

Eurodoc Statement on Representational Rights of ECRs

As institutions of higher education and research, the universities play a key role in and for democracies. The democratic mission of research and higher education in turn requires the promotion of **academic freedom, academic integrity, participation of the academic community in its governance, and institutional autonomy.**

Early career researchers (ECRs) are the future caretakers of higher education and research in Europe. Thus, it is essential that they partake not only in the tasks related to research, teaching, supervision, and outreach, but are also prepared for their responsibilities in ensuring trust in science and the democratic mission of higher education and research in Europe. Doctoral candidates, postdoctoral researchers, and other ECRs must be provided with **opportunities and quality training to prepare themselves for the role they have and will have** over the course of their careers as members of the academic community both within academia as well as in society more broadly. Furthermore, the policies of the European Higher Education Area and the European Research Area have mobility and exchange of the academic community at their core. It is thus crucial that **systemic barriers are consistently removed** such that international researchers can fully partake in academic governance.

It is **foundational that frameworks for academic governance support the effective participation of ECRs** for three reasons: for the realisation of the **EHEA fundamental values** and for the **quality of academic self-governance** in the present, and for ensuring **institutional autonomy in the future**. We call on the policy makers and the academic community to:

- **Ensure that no member of the academic community**, whether student, researcher, educator or other, **is left out from partaking in the EHEA fundamental values.**
- **Recognise that the academic community consists of different constituency groups**—such as students, researchers, educators on different education and career levels—for all of whom **adequate representation and participation in academic governance needs to be ensured.**
- **Acknowledge the very specific conditions of ECRs that differ from both students and permanent staff, such as short term contracts and high levels of internationalisation.** In order to ensure that ECRs at both **R1 and R2 level** can adequately partake in academic governance, **systemic barriers** (such as language barriers of committee work, of legal texts, and other frameworks) **must be reduced and frameworks for academic governance** (such as election cycles and mandated periods) must be such that each ECR **can reasonably enjoy their active and passive voting rights.**

About this statement

This statement was prepared by the board of Eurodoc 2024/2025 and adopted by the member organisations on the 26.05.2025. Contact: Eurodoc Board board@eurodoc.net

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Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of 26 national associations of early career researchers (ECRs) from 24 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research, higher education, and innovation in Europe.

